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CHILD'S PROPERTY RIGHTS

This scientific report provides an overview of the Bulgarian normative framework governing property rights of minors and legal actions pertaining to the disposition of property owned by minors and underage children. Proposals are made *de lege ferenda* for amendments to the existing legislation. The author proposes the expansion of the range of property which may be disposed by a minor after obtaining a court permission. The author also suggests that minors should be given the opportunity to perform smaller legal transactions on their own to meet their current needs.

Keywords: minor, child, property rights, disposition of property.

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IMOVINSKA PRAVA DETETA

U ovom naučnom izveštaju autor daje pregled normativnog okvira Republike Bugarske kojim se uređuju imovinska prava maloletnika i radnje koje se odnose na raspolaganje imovinom koja je u vlasništvu maloletnika i dece. Autor nudi predloge de lege ferenda u pogledu izmena postojećih zakona. Predlaže se proširenje kruga imovine za čije raspolaganje je potrebna dozvola suda. Autor takođe predlaže da se maloletnicima omogući da sami obavljaju manje pravne poslove kako bi zadovoljili svoje trenutne potrebe.

Ključne reči: maloletnik, dete, imovinska prava, raspolaganje imovinom.